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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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BIOTEXNOLOGIK USULLAR YORDAMIDA OLINGAN MAHSULOTLAR

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Annotatsiya: Biotexnologiya yordamida olingan mahsulotlar turli sohalarda, jumladan tibbiyot, qishloq xo'jaligi, oziq-ovqat sanoati va atrof-muhitni tozalashda katta ahamiyatga ega. Bu mahsulotlar inson salomatligini yaxshilash, qishloq xo'jaligini modernizatsiya qilish, va atrof-muhitni himoya qilishda muhim vositalardir.

Kalit so'zlar: Rekombinant insulin, *E. coli*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, Ekspressiya tizimi, Tripsin, Amiloza, Amilopektin

Hozirgi kunda Biotexnologiya yordamida insulin sintizi asosan rekombinant DNT texnologiyasi orqali amalga oshiriladi. Bu usulda genetik modifikatsiyalangan mikroorganizmlar (odamlar yoki boshqa organizmlarning genetik materialini o'zlashtirgan) insulin ishlab chiqaradi. **Insulin va uning ishlab chiqarilishi bo'yicha biotexnologiya jarayoni**

O'zbekistonda 2000-yilgacha bo'lgan ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, diabet kasalligi bilan og'riqan bemorlar soni 2 millionga yetgan, ya'ni aholi orasida 10% diabet kasalligi mavjud. Diabetni davolashda insulin ishlatiladi. O'sha paytlarda insulin, odatda, qoramolning oshqozon osti bezidan olinadi. Ammo bu insulin odam insulinini bilan mos kelmaydi. Diabetni davolashda biror vaqt yaxshi ta'sir qilsa ham, organizm unga vaqt o'tishi bilan o'rganib qoladi va insulin samaradorligi kamayadi. Shu sababli, so'nggi yillarda dunyoda "NOVA" firmasi odam insulinini ishlab chiqarishni boshladi. Insulinni olish jarayonida biotexnologik usullar qo'llaniladi. Bunda bakteriyalar, xususan, *E. coli* bakteriyasining K-12 shtammi ishlatiladi. Bu bakteriya kanomitsin antibiotigiga o'rgatiladi. Kanomitsin antibioitikini o'rgatilgan shtammdan foydalanish jarayonida, bakteriyalarni nobud qilmaslik uchun ularni kichik dozada berish kerak. Kanomitsin 0,01% dozada o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatadi, lekin ba'zi bakteriyalar, masalan, 20 million bakteriyadan 1 millioni nobud bo'lmasligi mumkin. Bundan keyin, nobud bo'lmagan bakteriyalar mikroskop ostida saralanadi. Kanomitsin konsentratsiyasi 0,02%, 0,05% va 1,0% gacha oshiriladi. Masalan, 1 milliondan 5000 ta bakteriya qoladi, va ular yana saralanadi. So'ngra 1,0% kanomitsin qo'llaniladi va natijada *E. coli* K-12 shtammi yaratiladi. Bu shtammning plazmidasida genetik ma'lumotlar mavjud, shuning uchun bu plazmida insulin ishlab chiqarish uchun kerakli genlar mavjud. Bakteriyani genetik manipulyatsiya qilishda **restriktaza fermentidan** foydalaniladi. Restriktaza

fermenti plazmida joylashgan insulin ishlab chiqarishga mas'ul genlarni ajratish uchun ishlatiladi. Bakteriyaning qobig'i yorilib, barcha zararsiz qobiq qismlari cho'kma holatida ajraladi, va sentrifugada ajratiladi. Tozalash jarayoni davomida plazmidni xromatografik usul bilan tozalash mumkin, va qobiqni muzlatib eritish orqali bakteriya hujayrasining qobig'i yoriladi. Keyingi bosqichda, *E. coli* bakteriyalarida proinsulin sintezi boshlanadi. Proinsulin esa keyinchalik insulinga aylanadi. Inson organizmida, aniqroq aytganda, Langergans orolchalarida insulin ishlab chiqaruvchi beta hujayralar mavjud. Ushbu hujayralarda proinsulin sintezi amalga oshiriladi. Langergans orolchalaridan olingan hujayralar maxsus eritmalarga joylashtiriladi va ular sekinlik bilan ko'payadi (taxminan 3-4 oy davomida).

Bu jarayon davomida, DNK orqali proinsulin sintezini amalga oshiradigan hujayralar ko'paytiriladi, va ular ichida insulin ishlab chiqarish uchun kerakli genlar ham mavjud. Insulin ishlab chiqarish jarayonida, agar insonning genetik xaritasi mavjud bo'lmasa, insulinga tegishli i-RNK yig'indisini ajratib olish mumkin. Bu yig'indining ichida insulin ishlab chiqarishga mas'ul bo'lgan RNK mavjud bo'ladi. Bu jarayonlarning asosiy maqsadi, insulin ishlab chiqarish uchun kerakli genlar va RNKlarni ajratib olishdir, bu esa natijada yuqori sifatli insulin ishlab chiqarish imkonini beradi. Shunday qilib, biotexnologiya yordamida insulin ishlab chiqarish jarayoni mikroorganizmlarni genetik modifikatsiya qilish orqali amalga oshiriladi, bu esa diabet kasalligini davolashda samarali va xavfsiz dori sifatida insulinni taqdim etadi. [1.2]

Shuningdek biotexnologiya yordamida tripsin fermentini olish texnologiyasi ishlab chiqilgan va amalga tadbiq etilgan. Tripsin fermentini olish texnologiyasi. Tripsin fermentini olish jarayoni oshqozon osti bezidan amalga oshiriladi va quyidagi bosqichlar orqali bajariladi:

Oshqozon osti bezini tayyorlash: Olish uchun oshqozon osti bezi volchokdan (maxsus uskunadan) o'tkaziladi. Bu jarayonning maqsadi zarrachaning disperslik darajasini 2-3 mm ga kamaytirishdir.

Disperslash: Oshqozon osti bezining xom ashyosi 18-20°C da 5 soat davomida saqlanadi. Bu usulda, biologik faol moddalar yengil tarqatilib, fermentning ajralishini ta'minlash uchun muhimdir.

Ekstraksiya: Ekstraksiya jarayonida 1,3% sulfat kislota bilan nordonlashtirilgan suv ishlatiladi. Ekstraksiya jarayoni muttasil aralashtirilib turiladi va 5°C da 32 soat davomida ikki marta olib boriladi. Birinchi ekstraksiyada ekstragentning hajmi xom ashyoga nisbatan 2:1 bo'ladi. Ikkinchi ekstraksiyada esa nisbat 1:1 bo'ladi. **Fraksiyali tuzlash:** Birinchi tuzlashda ekstraktga 242 mg sulfat ammoniy tuzi qo'shiladi. Tuzlash jarayonida tushgan cho'kma tashlab yuboriladi va quritib, pankreatin ishlab chiqarishda qo'shimcha sifatida ishlatiladi. **Ikkinchi tuzlash:** Birinchi tuzlashdan so'ng, cho'kma ustidagi suyuqlikka 2052 mg/l miqdorida sulfat ammoniy tuzi qo'shiladi va hosil bo'lgan oqsilli cho'kma ajratib olinadi. **Quritish:** Oqsilli cho'kmalar 25°C da vakuum quritkich shkafida quritiladi. Quritilgan preparat maydalanadi va elanishi amalga oshiriladi. **Qadoqlash:** Tayyor tripsin fermenti 50 g, 100 g, yoki 250 g li shisha idishlarga qadoqlanadi. Tayyor tripsin oqish kukun bo'lib, achchiq-sho'r ta'mga ega. U 1% gacha suvda va pH 7,0

da fosfat buferida yaxshi eriydi. Bu ferment boshqa fermentlar, masalan, **xemotripsin** bilan aralashgan holda ishlaydi. [1.3]

Bugungi kunda sanoat biotexnologiya yordamida o‘simliklarda kraxmal zaxira oziqa modda sifatida saqlanadi va kraxmal donachalari shaklida o‘zida to‘plangan bo‘ladi. Kraxmalning tarkibida ikkita asosiy komponent mavjud: **amiloza** va **amilopektin**.

Amiloza - bu shoxlanmagan, to‘g‘ri chiziqli zanjirdan iborat bo‘lib, issiq suvda tez eriydi va eritmaning qovushqoqligi kamayadi. Amiloza eritmalari beqaror bo‘lib, uzoq vaqt turish natijasida cho‘kma hosil qiladi. U yod eritmasi bilan reaksiyaga kirishganda ko‘k rangga bo‘yaladi.

Amilopektin - bu kuchli shoxlangan zanjirdan tashkil topgan va uning molekular hajmi 20—106 ga yetadi. Yod bilan reaksiyaga kirishganda kraxmal ko‘kimsir rangga bo‘yaladi. Kleysterga daraja ta’sir etilganda va yod tomizilganda uning rangi binafsha rangdan qizg‘ish ranggacha o‘zgaradi. O‘simliklarda kraxmalning tarkibidagi amiloza va amilopektinning nisbati turli o‘simliklarda farq qiladi. Bu nisbati o‘simliklarning kraxmal tarkibida qanday o‘zgarishlar yuz berishiniko‘rsatadi. [1.6.4]

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